

Synthesis of *p*-Phenylene-di-Acrylyl-*Bis*-*N*-Phenyl (PAPHA), Fumaryl-*Bis*-*N*-Phenyl (FPHA), Isophthalyl-*Bis*-*N*-Phenyl (IPHA) Hydroxamic Acids and Spectral and Magnetic Studies of their Polymers with Mn(II), Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II)

(MISS) N. R. GANDHI and K. N. MUNSHI

Department of Chemistry, Nagpur University, Nagpur-440 010

Three new *bis*-ligands, PAPHA, FPFA and IPHA have been synthesized and their polymers with Mn(II), Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) have been prepared. The compositions of the polymers have been proposed on the basis of elemental analysis, and their infrared and electronic spectra and magnetic susceptibilities have been reported. On the basis of these observations, their structures have been discussed.

EXCEPT for a cryptic mention of *bis*-hydroxamic acid-metal polymers¹, no other data appear to have been reported. A systematic study was therefore planned to undertake the synthesis of some *bis*-hydroxamic acids with the intention of studying their coordination polymers.

Experimental

The chemicals used were of AnalaR or chemically pure grade.

Preparation of the ligands :

In present investigations a modified method by Priyadarshini and Tandon² was used for the preparation of hydroxamic acids. In this procedure, freshly prepared *N*-hydroxylamine and vacuum distilled acid chloride in stoichiometric proportions are reacted at low temperature (0° or lower) in diethylether medium containing aqueous suspension of sodium bicarbonate.

Preparation of acid dichlorides : Dry acid (0.1 m) (*p*-phenylene-di-acrylic-, fumaric- or isophthalic-) and phosphorus pentachloride (0.2 m) were taken in a dry 250 ml round bottomed flask fitted with an air condenser provided with a guard tube filled with anhydrous CaCl₂. The mixture was heated on a water bath till a yellow pulverised mass in case of *p*-phenylene-di-acrylic acid (12 hr) and a clear liquid in case of fumaric (4 hr) or isophthalic (2 hr) acid was obtained. Phosphorus oxychloride was distilled off under reduced pressure and the acid chlorides extracted in ether. *p*-Phenylene-di-acrylyl chloride was a yellow solid, fumaryl chloride a liquid and isophthalyl chloride a colourless crystalline solid.

Preparation of *N*-phenylhydroxylamine : *N*-Phenylhydroxylamine was prepared by controlled reduction of nitrobenzene³.

Synthesis of PAPHA, FPFA and IPHA : Freshly prepared, crystallized, *N*-phenylhydroxylamine (0.25

m), diethylether (100 ml), sodium bicarbonate (0.3 m) and distilled water (30 ml) were taken in a 500 ml beaker and the mixture was cooled to 0° or below. To the above mixture, a solution of acid dichloride (0.1 m) in diethylether (150 ml) was added dropwise with constant stirring over about 1 hr. The product separated was filtered and washed thoroughly with saturated solution of NaHCO₃ to remove any acidic impurities.

These hydroxamic acids were crystallized from DMF-ethanol mixture. PAPHA and FPFA were yellow in colour (m.p.s. 225° and 194°, respectively), whereas IPHA was white (m.p. 180°). These hydroxamic acids have been reported for the first time in the present work and hence have been characterized on the basis of their elemental analysis and ir spectra. The results are given in Table 1 and Tables 5 to 7, respectively.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE LIGANDS

Sl. No.	Ligand	Analysis %		
		C Found (Calcd.)	H Found (Calcd.)	N Found (Calcd.)
1.	PAPHA	71.4 (72.0)	5.11 (5.00)	6.84 (7.00)
2.	FPFA	64.7 (64.4)	5.07 (4.69)	8.89 (9.39)
3.	IPHA	68.9 (68.9)	4.64 (4.59)	7.58 (8.04)

Synthesis of coordination polymers :

Polymers of PAPHA and FPFA with Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) : Metal solution prepared by dissolving metal acetate (0.01 m) in DMF (25 ml) was added to a solution of *bis*-hydroxamic acid prepared by dissolving the ligand (0.01 m) on DMF (25 ml). The reaction mixture was heated on a water bath with constant stirring till the polymer separated as an insoluble solid. It was

then digested on a water bath for about 2 hr. cooled to room temperature, filtered, washed thoroughly with DMF and ethanol and dried.

Polymers of IPHA with Mn(II), Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II): Zn(II) polymer was prepared by a method similar to the one described above. Other metals however failed to yield insoluble products with this ligand in DMF. These polymers were prepared by the following procedure.

Metal solution. prepared by dissolving metal acetate (0.01 m) [metal acetylacetonate in case of Fe(II)] in DMF (25 ml) was added to a solution of bis-hydroxamic acid prepared by dissolving the ligand (0.01 m) in dioxane (25 ml). The remaining procedure was the same as above.

Polymers of PAPHA and FPFA with Fe(II): Ligand (0.01 m), metal acetylacetonate (0.01 m), ethanol (25 ml) and DMF (25 ml) were taken in a 250 ml beaker. The remaining procedure was the same as above.

Physical measurements: Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made on the solid polymers at room temperature with Gouys balance, using mercury tetrathiocyanatocobalt(II) as standard. Diamagnetic corrections were calculated by the method given in literature⁴. Visible and ultraviolet spectra were recorded in 300-1000 nm range with Karl Zeiss USU-2-p spectrophotometer. Infrared

spectra of the ligands and the polymers were recorded on Specord-75 IR spectrophotometer in 400 to 4000 cm^{-1} region using nujol mull technique.

Results and Discussion

Tentative compositions for the polymers are proposed on the basis of elemental analysis. The proposed compositions, analytical data and colours of the polymers are reported in Tables 2 to 4. All polymers are insoluble in a wide variety of solvents and hence the products were purified by repeated washings with the solvents to remove all the unreacted metal ions and the ligand.

Infrared spectra: IR spectra of the polymers are practically identical. The frequency of some significant bands of the free ligand and of the metal-polymers are reported in Tables 5 to 7.

The free O-H stretching frequency appears at 3095 cm^{-1} in PAPHA, 3100 cm^{-1} in FPFA and at 3180 cm^{-1} in IPHA. Sharp band at 1595 cm^{-1} in PAPHA is assigned to C=O stretching vibration. Three consecutive bands at 1625, 1600 and 1570 cm^{-1} in FPFA and two bands at 1590 and 1610 cm^{-1} in IPHA are due to various resonating structures of R-N-OH. The N-O stretching vibration

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL DATA AND COLOURS OF METAL-PAPHA(L) POLYMERS

Sl. No.	Proposed composition of the polymer	Analysis %				Colour
		C Found (Calcd.)	H Found (Calcd.)	N Found (Calcd.)	M Found (Calcd.)	
1.	$\text{Mn}_x\text{L}_x(\text{OH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$	59.00 (59.48)	4.48 (4.03)	5.06 (5.78)	14.13 (14.18)	Dark brown
2.	$(\text{FeL}_2\text{H}_2\text{O})_n$	62.50 (58.79)	5.27 (4.49)	4.96 (5.72)	10.80 (11.40)	Red
3.	$(\text{CoL})_n$	59.00 (63.03)	3.78 (3.94)	5.21 (6.13)	12.60 (12.89)	Dark brown
4.	$\text{Ni}_x\text{L}(\text{OH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$	50.05 (49.19)	4.65 (4.10)	4.52 (4.78)	20.05 (20.06)	Greenish brown
5.	$(\text{CuL})_n$	63.00 (62.40)	4.40 (3.90)	5.38 (6.07)	12.76 (13.77)	Green
6.	$(\text{ZnL})_n$	61.10 (62.15)	4.18 (3.88)	5.75 (6.04)	13.23 (14.11)	Yellow

TABLE 3—ANALYTICAL DATA AND COLOURS OF METAL-FPFA (L) POLYMERS

Sl. No.	Proposed composition of the polymer	Analysis %				Colour
		C Found (Calcd.)	H Found (Calcd.)	N Found (Calcd.)	M Found (Calcd.)	
1.	$\text{Mn}_x\text{L}_x(\text{OH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$	50.20 (50.24)	4.63 (3.53)	6.76 (7.33)	16.56 (17.97)	Green
2.	$(\text{FeL}_2\text{H}_2\text{O})_n$	50.35 (49.50)	4.26 (4.12)	6.76 (7.22)	13.87 (14.40)	Red
3.	$(\text{CoL})_n\text{H}_2\text{O}$	50.25 (51.48)	4.46 (3.75)	7.12 (7.51)	15.97 (15.80)	Brownish yellow
4.	$(\text{NiL}_2\text{H}_2\text{O})_n2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	44.70 (44.99)	4.64 (4.67)	6.70 (6.56)	13.66 (13.76)	Yellow
5.	$(\text{CuL})_n$	52.80 (53.40)	3.84 (3.34)	7.78 (7.79)	17.27 (17.67)	Green
6.	$(\text{ZnL})_n$	53.00 (53.13)	4.34 (3.32)	6.55 (7.75)	16.89 (18.09)	Yellow

TABLE 4—ANALYTICAL DATA AND COLOURS OF METAL-IPHA(L) POLYMERS

Sl. No.	Proposed composition of the polymer	Analysis %				Colour
		C Found (Calcd.)	H Found (Calcd.)	N Found (Calcd.)	M Found (Calcd.)	
1.	$Mn_2L_2(OH)_2(H_2O)_2$	53.40 (54.23)	4.51 (3.61)	5.97 (6.33)	16.61 (16.55)	Greenish black Red
2.	$(FeL_2 \cdot 2H_2O)_n$	54.30 (54.81)	4.61 (4.11)	5.14 (6.39)	12.41 (12.75)	
3.	$(CoL_2 \cdot 2H_2O)_n$	53.00 (54.43)	5.58 (4.08)	5.64 (6.35)	12.87 (13.36)	Light pink Light green Green
4.	$(NiL_2 \cdot 2H_2O)_n \cdot 2H_2O$	49.90 (50.34)	4.16 (4.61)	5.35 (5.87)	12.06 (12.31)	
5.	$(CuL)_n$	57.40 (58.60)	3.80 (3.42)	6.74 (6.84)	15.29 (15.51)	White
6.	$Zn_2L_2(OH)_2(H_2O)_2$	49.65 (50.09)	4.14 (3.76)	5.16 (5.84)	20.84 (20.47)	

TABLE 5—INFRARED SPECTRAL DATA (4000-400 cm^{-1}) OF PAPHA AND POLYMERS

PAPHA	Mn(II)-polymer	Fe(II)-polymer	Co(II)-polymer	Ni(II)-polymer	Cu(II)-polymer	Zn(II)-polymer	Assignment
-	3200-3600 b	3200-3600 b	-	3200-3500 b	-	-	H-O-H
3095 m	-	-	-	-	-	-	O-H
1595 s	1550 bsh	1510 sh	1525 } m	1540 m	1500 sh	1515 bsh	C-O
970 s	950 s	1585 s	1545 } m	940 w	950 s	950 s	N-O
-	450 s	480 m	510 s	merged	570 s	520 m	M-O
-	555 m	545 s	-	-	-	555 w	-

b - broad ; s - strong ; bsh - broad shoulder ; m - medium ; sh - shoulder ; w - weak.

TABLE 6—INFRARED SPECTRAL DATA (4000-400 cm^{-1}) OF FPFA AND POLYMERS

FPFA	Mn(II)-polymer	Fe(II)-polymer	Co(II)-polymer	Ni(II)-polymer	Cu(II)-polymer	Zn(II)-polymer	Assignment
-	3200-3600 b	3200-3600 b	3200-3600 b	3200-3600 b	-	-	H-O-H
3100 m	-	-	-	-	-	-	O-H
1570 } s	1530 } s	1510 } s	1530 s	1525 } s	1535 } s	1525 s	C-O
1600 } s	1550 } s	1565 } s	1545 } sh	1540 } s	1535 } s	1560 m	
1625 } s	1555 } s	1575 } s	1575 } sh	1560 } s	1565 sh	-	-
965 s	960 s	950 s	955 s	950 s	950 s	950 w	N-O
-	470 s	495 s	495 s	475 s	475 s	490 w	M-O
-	580 w	580 w	570 w	-	-	570 w	-

b - broad ; s - strong ; sh - shoulder ; m - medium ; w - weak.

TABLE 7—INFRARED SPECTRAL DATA OF IPHA AND POLYMERS

IPHA	Mn(II)-polymer	Fe(II)-polymer	Co(II)-polymer	Ni(II)-polymer	Cu(II)-polymer	Zn(II)-polymer	Assignment
-	3300-3600 b	3250-3600 b	3200-3500 b	3200-3500 b	-	3200-3500 b	H-O-H
3180 m	-	-	-	-	-	-	O-H
1610 } s	1540 } s	1500 } s	1520 } s	1530 m	1530 } m	1525 m	C-O
1590 } s	1580 } s	1520 } s	1540 } s	-	1540 } m	-	
-	-	1570 sh	1555 } s	-	-	-	-
-	-	-	1570 } s	-	-	-	-
950 s	970 s	970 w	960 w	960 w	960 s	970 w	N-O
-	460 w	540 m	-	-	510 s	500 bsh	M-O

b - broad ; s - strong ; bsh - broad shoulder ; m - medium ; sh - shoulder ; w - weak.

is observed at 970, 965 and 950 cm^{-1} in PAPHA, FPFA and IPHA, respectively.

As anticipated, the O-H band disappears in the polymers. The carbonyl band is found to have been displaced towards lower frequency side indicating the formation of C—O...M coordinate bond.

N—O stretching band is reported to be shifted towards higher frequency side with an increase in intensity⁸. The same is observed in case of IPHA polymers. However, it is found to have been shifted towards lower frequency side in case of PAPHA and FPFA polymers. There is no significant increase in the intensity.

The presence of a band in the region 3200-3600 cm^{-1} indicates the O-H stretching vibration of lattice or coordinated water wherever it is present.

In all the cases the evidence of metal to oxygen (of the ligand) bonding is observed by a frequency at 450 to 615 cm^{-1} except in Co(II) and Ni(II)-IPHA polymers.

Electronic spectra and magnetic measurements

Electronic spectral data and magnetic data are summarised in Table 8.

TABLE 8—MAGNETIC AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF POLYMERS

Sl. No.	Polymer	Effective magnetic moment (kK) B. M.	Absorption bands	Assignment
1.	Mn-PAPHA	5.4187	28.57	${}^6A_1 \rightarrow {}^6E(D)$
			23.80	${}^6A_1 \rightarrow {}^6E(G)$
2.	Mn-FPFA	5.1584	27.77	${}^6A_1 \rightarrow {}^6E(D)$
3.	Mn-IPHA	5.2838	25.64	${}^6A_1 \rightarrow {}^6E(G)$
4.	Fe-PAPHA	5.3197	18.51	C. T.
5.	Fe-FPFA	5.3963	20.83	C. T.
6.	Fe-IPHA	5.2510	17.85 } 14.49 } 21.73 }	C. T.
7.	Co-PAPHA	5.1593	18.57 }	${}^4A_2 \rightarrow {}^4T_1(P)$
			26.31 }	C. T.
8.	Co-FPFA	4.5828	22.72 }	${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$
9.	Co-IPHA	4.9560	18.51 }	
			20.00 }	${}^3T_1 \rightarrow {}^3T_2(P)$
10.	Ni-PAPHA	3.1509	14.92 }	${}^3T_1 \rightarrow {}^3T_1(P)$
			12.82 }	${}^3T_1 \rightarrow {}^1E$
11.	Ni-FPFA	2.8866	26.31	${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ or C. T.
12.	Ni-IPHA	3.7521	22.72	${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$
			16.66	${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$
13.	Cu-PAPHA	1.9918	27.77	C. T.
14.	Cu-FPFA	1.8823	14.28	$d_{yz}, d_{xz} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$
			27.77	C. T.
			16.66	$d_{yz}, d_{xz} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$
			12.82	$d_{yz} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$
15.	Cu-IPHA	1.8096	32.72	C. T.
			13.33	$d_{yz}, d_{xz} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$

Mn(II)-polymers : In Mn(II)-PAPHA polymer, two strong bands are observed at 28.57 and 23.80 kK which are assigned to ${}^6A_1 \rightarrow {}^6E(D)$ and ${}^6A_1 \rightarrow {}^6E(G)$ excitations, respectively. Only one band appears in FPFA-polymer at 27.77 kK which can be assigned to ${}^6A_1 \rightarrow {}^6E(D)$ excitation and one band at 25.64 kK in IPHA-polymer can be assigned to ${}^6A_1 \rightarrow {}^6E(G)$ excitation.

Moderate intensity of these bands is indicative of tetrahedral geometry.

The values of magnetic moment correspond to d^5 , Mn(II) in all the polymers as reported in the literature⁶.

Fe(II)-polymers : One band at 18.51 kK in PAPHA-polymer and at 20.83 kK in FPFA-polymer may be conveniently assigned to charge transfer⁷. Two bands at 17.85 kK and 14.49 kK in IPHA-polymer may also be assigned to charge transfer.

The values obtained for the magnetic moment for all the polymers lie well within the range reported for octahedral high spin Fe(II) complexes.

Co(II)-polymers : Two bands at 21.73 kK and 18.57 kK in PAPHA-polymer are assigned to ${}^4A_2 \rightarrow {}^4T_1(P)$ excitation. Position of bands in the reflectance spectrum as well as magnetic moment of the Co(II)-PAPHA polymer suggest octahedral geometry. Elemental analysis, however, shows contradiction. Hence tetrahedral geometry is suggested for this polymer.

One band at 26.31 kK in FPFA-polymer can be assigned to charge transfer. The spectrum of this polymer surprisingly does not show any band in the near infrared or visible region which can be assigned to d-d transition. Magnetic moment, and composition proposed on the basis of elemental analysis suggest tetrahedral geometry.

Two bands at 22.72 kK and 18.51 kK in IPHA-polymer can be assigned to ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transition suggesting octahedral geometry. Magnetic moment lies slightly lower than the calculated one which may be accounted for high orbital contribution.

Ni(II)-polymers : In FPFA-polymer a band appears at 26.31 kK which is assigned to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transition or charge transfer. A band at 22.72 kK in IPHA-polymer can be assigned to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transition and at 16.66 kK to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ transition. This is in good agreement with Liehr and Ballhausen⁹ energy level diagram for Ni(II) ion in octahedral geometry.

The magnetic moment for Ni(II)-FPFA polymer lies well within the range generally reported for octahedral Ni(II) complexes¹⁰. The higher value obtained for IPHA-polymer may be due to the departure from octahedral geometry towards tetragonal (D_{4h}) geometry¹¹.

In Ni(II)-PAPHA polymer, a shoulder at 20.00 kK and two bands at 14.92 kK and 12.82 kK are assigned to ${}^3T_1 \rightarrow {}^3T_2(P)$, ${}^3T_1 \rightarrow {}^3T_1(P)$ and ${}^3T_1 \rightarrow {}^1E$ excitations, respectively indicating tetrahedral geometry. The value for magnetic moment lies lower than the value generally reported for tetrahedral Ni(II) complexes.

Cu(II)-polymers : In all the Cu(II)-polymers charge transfer bands are observed on higher frequency side of the spectra. Besides these, weaker bands are observed at 14.28 kK, 16.66 kK and 13.33 kK in PAPHA-, FPFA- and IPHA-polymers, respectively which are assigned to $d_{yz}, d_{xz} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$

transition. One more band at 12.82 kK in FPFA-polymer is assigned to $d_{z^2} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ transition.

From the reflectance spectra, all the Cu(II)-polymers can be assigned a distorted tetrahedral geometry. Magnetic data, however, show contradiction and suggest square planar geometry.

Zn(II)-polymers: These are diamagnetic and on the basis of elemental analysis, are suggested to be tetrahedral.

Proposed structures

The characterization of the polymers prepared in the present investigation is difficult because of their insolubility and intractability. Their formation as polymers from steric considerations and assignment of degree of polymerization on the basis of elemental analysis are tentative.

The composition has been suggested on the basis of elemental analysis (Tables 2 to 4), which is explained later with the help of ir spectra, magnetic

and reflectance studies and tentative structures have been proposed for these compounds.

The structures given for coordination polymers are always questionable. A simple linear, two dimensional planar or three dimensional structures are possible when the metal is coordinated to two, three or four ligand molecules, respectively. In the case of the polymer derived from methylene-bis-(5-salicylaldehyde) it has been suggested on the basis of some physico-chemical studies that two or three dimensional lattice structure predominates^{1,2}. If the degree of polymerization is limited to certain extent then in such type of polymers the metal to ligand compositions may not correspond to that of linear chain polymer. Keeping these in view, linear chain unit structures proposed for the polymers may be taken as tentative ones.

Observations of the composition of some of the compounds lead to the conclusion that they should be simple polynuclear complexes, but their extreme

TABLE 9—PROPOSED STRUCTURES OF THE POLYMERS

Metal						
Mn(II)	$n = 4$	Where R =				
Ni(II)	$n = 1$					
Mn(II)	$n = 3$	Where R =				
Zn(II)	$n = 2$	Where R =				
Mn(II)	$n = 3$					
Fe(II)		Where R =				
Fe(II)		Where R =				
Ni(II)						
Fe(II)		Where R =				
Ni(II)						
Co(II)						
Co(II)		Where R =				
Cu(II)						
Zn(II)						
Co(II)		Where R =				
Cu(II)						
Zn(II)						
Cu(II)		Where R =				

insolubility makes one believe in their polymeric nature with more complex features present. The association of these low molecular weight units through hydrogen bonding or polymerization, making use of hydroxyl as bridging groups, cannot be ruled out. The structures proposed in Table 9 should therefore be taken as tentative in the light of the above discussion.

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